

Ecological Atrocity in Indian Blue: Reimagining Blue Humanities through an Indian Ecocritical Perspective

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Abstract: *Water has always been an essential element in the structure of universal existence that interweaves human lives, emotions, philosophy, culture, and countless other dimensions of experience. The exploration of these dimensions has brought the field of Blue Humanities into the light, offering a perspective, though recently formalised, that draws upon concepts and connections that have existed since time immemorial. This article employs the lens of blue humanities to promote a relational understanding of the Indian rivers and ecological degradation. Indian rivers are not merely scenic or functional landscapes, but they are dynamic, living forces that have shaped cultural identity, social structures, spiritual traditions, and ecological systems for thousands of years. This article accentuates a dystopian narrative that anchors political satire and ecological absurdism to critique India's contemporary environmental collapse and neoliberal complexities of water as a resource through an analysis of Sarnath Banerjee's "All Quiet in Vikaspuri". The central motif of the novel revolves around the plumber's surreal quest to retrieve the mythical Saraswati River. This quest questions the myth, consumerism, scarcity, and hydro-political inequalities that act as a significant intervention in the contemporary ecoliterary discourse.*

Keywords - Blue Humanities, Ecocriticism, Graphic Novel, Indian Rivers

Introduction

While our world is deeply connected to nature, we cannot overlook the fact of degradation within ecological sustainability. As the global economy continues to evolve, the exacerbation of environmental issues has become increasingly concerning to the world, affecting multidimensional aspects of the national economy, society, and environment. Mindless consumerism and economic growth have become distinctive characteristics of the present ecological degradation, which appears more anthropogenic than natural. Ecoliteracy was initially overlooked as a legislative issue for a long time; however, this changed with the creation of the United Nations Development Group (UNEP) in 1972 under the direction of Maurice Strong. It facilitated the development and implementation of several multilateral environmental agreements, including the Minamata Convention on Mercury, the Montreal Protocol, and a range of international environmental initiatives. In the Indian milieu, ecological governance has made significant progress through engagement with the Millennium Development Goals. It has since been aligned with the Sustainable Development Goals to be achieved by 2030 under NITI Aayog's national implementation and monitoring.

In the current global scenario, the practical implementation of technological interventions for environmental protection has become a critical area of focus, with continuous awareness and ecoliteracy being undertaken to foster a more sustainable world. To establish its importance to a broader audience, many scholars and researchers choose to adopt writing and pedagogical practices that disseminate environmental awareness "To enhance people's understanding of anthropocentric approach towards the environment, the need for innovation in the education system is needed" (Abinaya 191). The panoptic observation of this study points out the acute degradation of the water system, accentuating it as a critical site of environmental crisis. The article narrows its scope and advances towards the framework of Blue Humanities in relation to Indian rivers, offering a critical view of rich mythical,

cultural and civilizational dimensions of these rivers being threatened by modern evolution and environmental destruction. Indian Literature, which was once limited to the specific genre of nobles, saints and mythological elements, broke its barrier during the colonisation and independence struggle. 19th-century writers were influenced by American and British writers, resulting in the expansion and collaboration of society over literature. The composition of the extraordinary works of Amitav Ghosh's 'The Hungry Tide' and 'Gun Island', Mahasweta Devi's 'Aranyer Adhikar', and Kiran Desai's 'The Inheritance of Loss' foreground the dominant relationship of humans over nature. This article significantly investigates ecological deterioration in Sarnath Banerjee's work, attributing it to the dominant discourse of ecological crises surrounding Indian rivers as the novel's quintessential narrative structure, grasping the complexities of river degradation, water scarcity, and hydropolitical anxieties in modern Indian narratives.

Congruence of Blue Humanities in 'All Quiet in Vikaspuri'

English literature, which was once rooted in land-based perspectives, began to shift its focus toward the seas and oceans, and was largely influenced by the pioneering work of Steve Mentz. In 2009, literary scholar Steve Mentz coined the phrase 'Blue cultural studies,' also known as Blue humanities, which proffers a broader platform for scholars to explore the diverse dimensions of this emerging genre. Water was once merely a figurative element, but now it plunges into the deeper layer of literature, illuminating the social, cultural, and religious texture of past works, while revealing the profound connections between aquatic imagery and the human psyche, especially under the scholarly guidance of figures like Dan Brayton, Hester Blum, and Steve Mentz. In the present day, blue humanities functions as a vibrant and inclusive field of literary inquiry, fostering global innovation and enabling representation of diverse ethnic and cultural identities. "We must view the ocean not as a placeless expanse but as a space produced through human histories, economies, and ecologies, which

continuously evolve through interactions between people, non-human organisms, and material forces”(Peters and Steinberg 158).

India is deeply rooted in water, a heritage closely tied to its society, culture, and religion, offering an abundance of literary resources that date back to the earliest periods of human civilisation. Thus, when we discuss ecocriticism in the context of Blue Humanities, ‘All Quiet in Vikaspuri’ clearly resonates with the purpose. The protagonist of the novel, Girish, a plumber struggling to break free from the shackles of the collapsed industrial township of Tambapur, travels in search of a livelihood and meaning in Delhi, “the doomed procession of displaced thousands” (Banerjee 16). His absurd confrontation with Rastogi, a bureaucratic figure obsessed with locating the mythical Indian river Saraswati, becomes his inducement “Girish, in the story, finds himself tweaking in underground labour, drilling for water for the Pataal Jal project” (Ajay and Prakash 338). Through this unlikely alliance, Banerjee presents a paradoxical and unsettling portrayal of Delhi’s brewing water crisis, connoting the city’s parched landscape and dysfunctional water infrastructure. Girish’s ensuing journey to trace the lost Saraswati in this context is not just a physical survival quest but also a symbolic exploration. While he adventures toward the solution of metamorphosed desperation, he encounters a series of individuals who are subsumed by the pursuit of a vanishing water source. Among them is Jagat Singh, an illegal water supplier who diverts public water to private tankers, leaving them in a precarious survival situation. Rajen, another crippling character, highlights the hegemony of elites who commodify water by selling it to the elite of Delhi. The systemic denunciation of the late Colonel Gambhir and Awasthy culminates in the vulnerability of the crisis, particularly in his personal act of exploiting public resources for private gain, exacerbating the state’s inefficiencies. Banerjee’s careful construction of Philippa Carry-Jones’s extravagant and unsustainable water consumption openly portrays her as oblivious to the growing crisis “Ms Carrey Jones was weary of dirt and germs of India and tried to protect herself at all cost.” (Banerjee 38), “Every time the child peed in the pool, she had it

drained and refilled with fresh water” (Ibid, 38), thereby satirically exposing the realities of Delhi’s water crisis, revealing the cascading confluence of degraded ecology and socio-political hypocrisy.

The fractured visual and textual elements collectively justify the text’s engagement with the central concerns of Blue Humanities, where each character’s trajectory is intricately shaped by water scarcity and the obsessive quest for a mythological river broadens the violation of water deprivation, hydro-politics, and corrupt bureaucratic conduct.

Anatomy of Ecocriticism via graphic narratives

The fusion of sustainability and graphic novels as a substantial part of popular culture is particularly relevant to the postmodern reader who is more fascinated by the growing digital aspects. The exaggerated visual and textual graphics expose the paradoxical relationship to the deterioration of nature, concurrently trendy within the popular cultural industry. The subject matter of this genre can address various social, political, or cultural issues, specifically tailored for the adult audience, and confronts traumatic visuals, parodies of classical texts, historical events, or even films. The diverse readers of India gained momentum with the multilingual advancement of narrative structures, which has permanently dominated the adversity of this genre within the culture industry. Indian diversity is at the core of social issues, thus providing a fertile ground for graphic novels, where the satire and parody are not adaptations of literary texts but rather intentional and relevant to contemporary society. Indian Graphic novelists often consider Orijit Sen’s ‘River of the Stories’ as India’s first successful graphic novel, which predominantly questions the social and political issues concerning the controversial construction of the Naramada dam, reflecting the environmental crisis at deposition. Apart from that, *The Harappa Files*, *The Barn Owl’s Wondrous Capers*, and *Delhi Calm* are a few examples that can be considered as a medium of expansion of this literary genre.

‘All Quiest in Vikaspuri’ certainly virtualises the predominant topic of ecological disputes within the dystopian city of Delhi, Bannerjee’s extraordinary characterisation of narratives culminates in satire and paradox of urban city with purging circulation of water conflicts surrounding the different categorical strata of individuals. The ambitious Smart City Mission of Delhi is highly satirical in its portrayal of the transcendental shift from industrial growth of Tambhapur to mortified worker protests and ultimately privatisation “When industries take over agricultural land and dams drown entire villages and destroy settled communities to produce unjustifiable low amounts of electricity” (Banerjee 56) which forces our protagonist to approach Delhi as a path to rejuvenation. Banerjee’s pick for Delhi is crucial as it dissipates the utmost urgency of ethical governance foreshadowed by bureaucratic hydro-politics in the crisis of water, the utmost necessity of living beings. The various individuals and their approaches to addressing the urban crisis concern us with holistic ecological degradation and how all these individuals are using this degradation not as a crisis but as an opportunity for their own gain. Water here acts as a bracing factor both mythologically and realistically. On one hand, they refuse to acknowledge the growing concerns of the marginalised population, and ironically, on the other hand, the quest for the river Saraswati, which, according to Indian mythology, had vanished, is finally answered at the end of the novel. The reader's perpetual attempt to understand the facts and narrativization surrounding the physical reality is ironic in light of the author’s intentional use of the river Saraswati, which in the contemporary world remains unknown, as the source explains an ironic twist and the modern sick mindset and urge for realistic resolution.

Thus, the work’s illustration of a decaying city not only generalises the concept of environmental privatisation, hydrological commodification, and lack of governance, but also highlights the marginalised community as the sole victim of this crisis, perfectly stimulating the discussion of this article.

Conclusion

“The ocean is central to understanding capitalism’s ecological crisis, as it has been a site of exploitation, transportation, and resource extraction, often viewed as limitless but now increasingly recognised as finite and fragile” (Gerhardt et. al 6) has been explicitly pictured in Sarnath Banerjee’s ‘All Quiet in Vikaspuri’. This article brings one of the dominant genres of Indian literature into the light of Blue Humanities, interconnecting with possible narratives. A consistent exploitation of nature, a processed violence of unmindful consumption under the supervision of the State Apparatus, consuming us bit by bit. The necessity of ecoliteracy is more evident now than ever. The current ecological atrocity did not stop till water extended to every province of environmental pollution. While Banerjee is describing dystopian Delhi in the post-19th century, it ironically matches the current scenario of Delhi. The novel's extraordinary ornamentation of narratives and their diverse situations remains coherent despite despair; individuals' hidden moral bankruptcy unveils the moral insensitivity and necessity for ecoliteracy. The use of hydro-politics enlightens readers to another side of the novel, dissecting the characters, their actions and most importantly, the use of speech and dialogue. Banerjee explored the part of water scarcity and pollution under the then political circumstances, which perfectly fits the research behind the paper, comprising diversity within the graphic novels.

This paper dives into the characters and interprets the novel through the lens of water literature, which is substantial to the emerging scholarly impression. India, being diverse in its own geographical structure and culturally established, allows the growth of new works and sustained academic research in Blue Humanities.

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